

Status and Pedogenetic Distribution of Selected Extractable Micronutrients in Mambilla Plateau-Montane Soils of Nigeria

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Abstract

Mambilla Plateau is widely utilized for agricultural production, not much is known about the pedogenic concentration of the soil micronutrients there. The purpose of this study was to assess the pedogenic concentration and current state of a few selectable micronutrients in a few soil samples from the Mambilla Plateau in Taraba State, Northeastern Nigeria. Twelve profile pits in all were excavated to serve as sampling units. The profile pits' pedogenetic strata provided samples of soil, which were then gathered, processed, and examined. The profile pits' sand content ranged from 28.24 to 86.88 %. Total exchangeable bases ranged from low to medium (4.58 to 9.17 cmol kg⁻¹), organic carbon (OC) varied from low to high (2.40 to 36.00 g/kg), and soil pH varied from slightly acidic to highly acidic (5.15 to 6.32). Cu(2.8–5.3 mg kg⁻¹) was over the critical limit, but available Zn(0.010–0.022 mg kg⁻¹), Cu(0.020–0.034 mg kg⁻¹), and Fe(0.21–0.45 mg kg⁻¹) were below it. Sand and OC showed a significantly substantial positive association with available Zn, Cu, and Fe. There would be a need to apply soil amendments to supplement the soil with micronutrients for successful and profitable crop production.

Keywords: Mambilla Plateau; micronutrients; soil properties; soil relationships

Introduction

Mambilla Plateau is an area where most of her populace are basically agrarians. Because of this, there has been constant, intense farming, which lowers soil micronutrient levels. According to Yusufu and Abenu (2019), a reduction in soil micronutrients impedes plant growth at its best and agricultural sustainability. According to Kingsley et al. (2019), micronutrients are metallic chemical elements that plants need in small amounts. They are also crucial as macronutrients in terms of agronomy. These elements, which include copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), and zinc (Zn), among others, are essential for the

biosynthesis of protein, the production of vitamin A in plants, growth factors, the metabolism of carbohydrates and fats through their participation in various plant enzymatic systems, the regulation of respiration and photosynthesis, the enhancement of plant tissues' ability to hold water (Mulima et al., 2015; FAO, 2011). According to the evaluations of soil micronutrients, there is relatively little difference in the limits for sufficient, deficient, and harmful amounts. Studies by Domchang et al. (2014) and Oluwadare et al. (2013) indicated that micronutrient deficiencies have been identified more often in the past few years. The erroneous and inappropriate application of fertilizers may be the cause of these deficits. According to Hassan and Ogbonnaya (2016), one of the key factors that caused agrarians to recognize the importance of balanced fertilization in crop productivity was their realization of micronutrient deficiencies in the soil.

The distribution of soil micronutrients might differ among profiles created using various parent materials and landforms (Verma et al., 2005). Micronutrient removal from the soil has increased dramatically since high-yielding enhanced cultivars were introduced. The earth minerals found in the pedosphere are what replenish micronutrients in soils. Micronutrients in soil vary geographically as a result of pedospheric differences brought about by parent material, terrain, climate, etc. (Katyal and Sharma, 1991). In order to address the issues related to soil micronutrient deficiencies, it is now crucial to evaluate the micronutrient status of soils and make the necessary corrections. According to Bichi and Ibrahim (2018), agricultural output is controlled by the most limiting factor, hence efforts to increase crop productivity through watering, fertilizing, and other means may be ineffective even if a single micronutrient turns out to be a limiting factor. In the majority of Nigeria's soils, the reduction in soil fertility brought on by micronutrient deficiencies is turning into a serious problem. As a result, sufficient information regarding the soil's innate ability to give nutrients from lower soil layers must be gathered in order to adjust nutrients in the field effectively (Setia and Sharma, 2004). The distribution of nutrients in soils is closely related to pedogenic development.

Few or no studies have looked at how soil micronutrient concentration relates to profile depth in the Mambilla Plateau to promote agricultural production and ecosystem balance. The information provided by this study is necessary to comprehend the condition and variability of micronutrients in the different soil types found in the Mambilla Plateau. Planning soil management treatments to maintain micronutrient levels at adequate levels and address deficiencies in the study site will benefit from the data collected.

Materials and Methods

The Mambilla Plateau (Fig. 1), whose total land area is 3,765.2 km², is situated between latitudes 6° 30' 24" to 7° 19' 48" N and longitudes 11° 02' 42" to 11° 37' 12" E. It forms the southernmost tip of Nigeria's northeast region. The Sardauna Local Government Area in Taraba State Northeast, Nigeria, encompasses the entire plateau. With peaks in June/July and September, the average yearly rainfall ranges from 1780 mm to 2200 mm (Chapman and Chapman, 2000). Between 25 and 35 degrees Celsius is the average yearly temperature (Bami, 2013). The Nigerian Montane Guinea Savanna zone includes the Mambilla Plateau. The plateau's vegetation consists mostly of short grasses, with very few trees—aside from artificial forests—growing on it. The geology of the Mambilla Plateau is

developed on Basement Complex rocks. Using a flexible grid sample technique, a total of 12 profile pits measuring 2 m × 1.8 m × 2 m were dug, one on each grid. Soil Survey Staff (2017) provided instructions for the description and sampling of the profile pits. For standard laboratory analysis, the samples were air-dried, crushed, and put through a 2.0 mm and 0.5 mm mesh sieve. The following characteristics of the soil were found. The Bouyoucos hydrometer method was used to determine the particle size distribution (Gee and Or, 2002). Using a glass electrode pH meter with a solid-liquid (water) ratio of 1:2.5, the pH of the soil was measured electrometrically (Thomas, 1996). According to Thomas's (1982) instructions, exchangeable bases were identified using the neutral ammonium acetate method buffered at pH 7.0. The wet digestion procedure as outlined by Nelson and Sommers (1982) was used to measure total carbon. According to Sahlemedhin and Taye (2000), the available micronutrients (iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and manganese (Mn)) were extracted using DTPA, and an atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used to test each micronutrient.

Fig. 1. Map of the Mambilla Plateau

Results and Discussion

According to the results (Table 1), the horizons' sand content ranged from 28.24 to 86.88 % throughout the profiles. In every soil horizon of the profiles that were examined, sand content predominated the mineral fraction. This may be partially explained by parent material that was high in quartz mineral, which is a necessary ingredient in granite Wilson (2010). Sand often makes up the majority of the soil's particle size fraction, followed by clay and then silt. Osujieke *et al.* (2018; 2020) and Lawal *et al.* (2013) have revealed comparable outcomes in their studies conducted within the Guinea savannah region of Nigeria.

With the exception of profiles 6 and 8, whose sand content declined with profile depth in a regular pattern, the distribution of sand content in the profiles showed an erratic pattern

as it decreased. The silt fraction varied between the profiles, ranging from 3.28 to 37.20 %. There is no clear pattern in the silt content distribution pattern with respect to profile depth. The profiles' horizons showed a range of 7.28 to 62.48 % of clay concentration. With the exception of profiles 6 and 8, which exhibited a consistent pattern of decline with profile depth, the clay content values in the majority of profiles lacked a clear pattern of distribution. Variations in the weathering of parent material may be linked to the irregular pattern in clay distribution with profile depth (Sekhar et al., 2014).

Table 1. *Physico-chemical properties of the soils of Mambilla Plateau*

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand →	Silt %	Clay ←	pH (H ₂ O)	OC (g/kg)	TEB →	ECEC ←
Profile 1 (Jabu) (N06°53'52.8" E011°24'13.9" and elevation= 1567 m)								
Ap	0 – 29	74.80	11.00	14.20	5.70	34.90	7.06	8.14
Bt1	29 – 48	62.80	11.00	26.20	5.78	15.60	5.94	6.94
Bt2	48 – 71	67.80	12.00	20.20	5.83	14.40	6.22	7.31
Bt3	71 – 86	65.80	11.00	23.20	5.81	15.20	6.23	7.30
Bt4	86 – 120	64.80	12.00	23.20	5.81	16.60	6.00	7.06
Bt5	120 – 180	58.80	17.00	24.20	5.78	25.10	7.56	8.58
Profile 2 (Tonga Shaibu) (N06° 51'11.5" E011°23'06.05" and elevation= 1435 m)								
Ap	0 – 54	54.24	11.28	34.48	5.31	24.50	8.91	9.99
Bt1	54 – 85	38.24	13.28	48.48	5.82	20.70	6.12	7.15
Bt2	85 – 126	45.24	9.28	45.48	5.78	19.00	7.41	8.45
Bt3	126 – 144	46.24	9.28	44.48	5.84	16.60	6.42	7.45
Bt4	144 – 160	44.24	9.28	46.48	5.80	15.40	5.95	6.96
Profile 3 (Dembe) (N06°45'05.30" E011°20'02.7" and elevation= 1275 m)								
Ap	0 – 30	28.88	23.28	47.84	6.24	17.80	7.00	8.15
A	30 – 39	74.88	11.28	13.84	6.17	11.00	6.47	7.56
AB1	39 – 49	52.88	23.28	23.84	6.16	15.60	6.05	7.10
AB2	49 – 60	76.88	11.28	13.84	6.14	18.40	6.12	7.16
Bt	60 – 70	34.88	29.28	35.84	6.20	21.10	7.25	8.27
C1	70 – 83	82.88	5.28	11.84	6.16	13.40	5.32	6.32
C2	83 – 106	86.88	3.28	9.84	6.17	9.00	5.72	6.88
Profile 4 (Kune) (N06°43'24.4" E011°21'56.7" and elevation= 1271 m)								
Ap	0 – 32	65.80	10.00	24.20	5.88	21.50	5.85	6.91
A1	32 – 65	66.80	12.00	21.20	5.70	13.40	6.86	6.97
A2	65 – 90	69.80	11.00	19.20	5.68	13.20	5.45	6.49
A3	90 – 113	66.80	13.00	20.20	5.68	7.20	6.10	7.13
A4	113 – 138	72.80	14.00	13.20	5.71	12.00	6.21	7.25
Bt1	138 – 165	67.80	10.00	22.20	5.15	7.60	6.05	7.07
Bt2	165 – 200	63.80	13.00	23.20	5.16	7.20	5.44	6.51
Profile 5 (Mbanga) (N06°37'03.4" E011°12'28.1" and elevation= 1481 m)								
Ap	0 – 40	86.24	5.28	8.48	5.66	20.50	7.42	8.50
A	40 – 89	78.24	13.28	8.48	5.68	12.40	4.99	6.00
Bt1	89 – 122	58.24	17.28	24.48	5.68	9.40	4.66	5.64
Bt2	122 – 160	28.24	37.28	34.48	5.76	18.60	7.23	8.27
C	160 – 200	74.24	11.28	14.48	5.76	20.30	5.82	6.83
Profile 6 (Dung) (N06°40'34.1" E011°18'27.4" and elevation= 1272 m)								
Ap	0 – 25	65.24	18.28	16.48	5.75	11.80	5.67	6.73
Bt1	25 – 49	36.24	17.28	46.48	5.60	6.20	4.91	5.92
Bt2	49 – 130	30.24	9.28	60.48	5.55	2.40	4.58	5.60
Bt3	130 – 200	28.24	9.28	62.48	5.54	5.40	4.81	5.80

OC= organic carbon, TEB= total exchangeable bases, ECEC= effective cation exchange capacity

Table 1. *Physico-chemical properties of the soils of Mambilla Plateau (cont'd)*

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand →	Silt %	← Clay	pH (H ₂ O)	OC (g/kg)	TEB → cmol/kg ←	ECEC
Profile 7 (Leme) (N06°45'15.1" E011°12'34.6" and elevation= 1539 m)								
A	0 – 11	74.24	11.28	14.48	5.73	36.00	8.61	9.69
Bt1	11 – 42	56.24	15.28	28.48	5.70	20.90	6.52	7.56
Bt2	42 – 71	56.24	13.28	30.48	5.67	18.20	7.60	8.65
Bt3	71 – 87	62.24	9.28	28.48	5.68	26.10	8.69	9.78
Bt4	87 – 120	64.24	9.28	26.48	5.66	20.30	6.59	7.62
C1	120 – 164	87.24	4.28	8.48	5.61	27.90	9.05	10.12
C2	164 – 200	89.24	3.28	7.48	5.63	33.30	9.17	10.28
Profile 8 (Yerimaru) (3N06°47'39.4" E011°02'42.1" and elevation= 1522 m)								
Ap	0 – 25	72.24	7.28	20.48	6.03	26.00	6.10	7.16
Bt1	25 – 45	48.24	9.28	42.48	5.98	11.80	8.16	9.30
Bt2	45 – 115	40.24	13.28	46.48	5.96	12.00	8.15	9.29
Bt3	115 – 132	38.24	13.28	48.48	5.92	12.00	6.95	8.04
Bt4	132 – 200	38.24	13.28	48.48	5.89	9.00	6.97	8.04
Profile 9 (Furumi) (N06°53'51.8" E011°04'00.7" and elevation= 1497 m)								
Ap	0 – 21	74.24	11.28	14.48	5.68	21.50	5.21	6.29
Bt1	21 – 35	48.24	9.28	42.48	5.78	24.50	6.13	7.23
Bt2	35 – 100	38.24	13.28	48.48	5.88	20.90	7.02	8.14
Bt3	100 – 140	48.24	13.28	38.48	5.89	16.60	5.25	6.32
Bt4	140 – 186	48.24	9.28	42.48	5.92	15.40	6.12	7.21
Bt5	186 – 200	46.24	9.28	44.48	5.92	6.40	6.09	7.19
Profile 10 (Nguroje) (N06°53'00.8" E011°07'54.8" and elevation= 1499 m)								
Ap	0 – 30	76.88	5.28	17.84	6.06	32.90	7.46	8.63
Bt1	30 – 62	54.88	9.28	35.84	6.10	27.70	7.26	8.41
Bt2	62 – 93	68.88	7.28	23.84	6.15	12.80	6.67	7.71
Bt3	93 – 122	36.88	17.28	45.84	6.17	14.40	6.61	7.64
Bt4	122 – 140	36.88	17.28	45.84	6.16	12.40	6.43	7.46
Bt5	140 – 180	42.88	13.28	43.84	6.19	7.40	5.62	6.65
Profile 11 (NgelNyake) (N07°05'27.6" E011°05'17.0" and elevation= 1608 m)								
Ap	0 – 34	62.24	9.28	28.48	5.90	34.10	6.93	8.05
A	34 – 87	82.24	7.28	10.48	5.94	34.90	6.28	7.34
BA	87 – 114	62.24	9.28	28.48	5.94	24.20	6.25	7.32
Bt1	114 – 132	46.24	9.28	44.48	5.96	11.80	5.20	6.25
Bt2	132 – 158	46.24	9.28	44.48	5.95	9.40	5.13	6.16
Bt3	158 – 200	44.24	9.28	46.48	6.00	8.00	5.06	6.08
Profile 12 (Maisamari) (N07°10'16.1" E011°05'09.0" and elevation= 1440 m)								
Ap	0 – 20	76.80	11.00	12.20	5.74	26.40	6.44	7.57
A1	20 – 43	77.80	10.00	12.20	5.84	27.10	6.11	7.16
A2	43 – 84	74.80	12.00	13.20	6.32	18.00	6.57	7.70
A3	84 – 111	78.80	11.00	10.20	6.31	31.00	8.14	9.24
A4	111 – 174	78.80	10.00	11.20	6.15	33.70	7.37	8.41
AB	174 – 200	72.80	10.00	17.20	6.08	17.80	6.66	7.69

OC= organic carbon, TEB= total exchangeable bases, ECEC= effective cation exchange capacity

However, Abagyeh et al. (2019) found that the vertical translocation of clay through the processes of lessivage and illuviation may be responsible for the overall rise in clay content with profile depth. The Fig 2 shows the interaction between the particle size fractions.

Fig. 2. Interaction between the particle size distribution

The findings (Table 1) indicated that the pH (H₂O) values of the soil varied from 5.15 to 6.32. Based on Chude et al. (2011) evaluations, the pH of the soil varied from slightly acidic to extremely acidic in the horizons of the profiles. Nevertheless, the soil pH result does not agree with the results of Hassan et al. (2015) in Nigeria's Plateau State's basaltic soils. An inconsistent increase or reduction in soil pH was noted as profile depth increased. On the soil of the Northern Nigerian savanna, researchers Domchang et al. (2014) and Sharu et al. (2013) noted similar pH levels and attributed the results to the parent material's composition, the leaching of basic cations from the soil surface to lower depths, and the frequent use of acid-forming fertilizers such as urea. The usage of ammonia-based fertilizer, frequent clearance of plant debris, and bush burning may all be contributing factors to the low pH in the majority of the profiles. The horizons' values for organic carbon content in the profiles varied from 2.40 to 36.00 g/kg. Based on Esu's (1991) evaluations, the profiles' organic carbon content ranged from low to high. Climate and leaching may have an impact on the rate of change of organic carbon over the horizons of the profiles. Numerous writers (Osujieke et al., 2019 and Fasina et al., 2015) have also noted low levels of organic carbon in savanna zone soils and have linked this to ongoing plant residue burning and cultivation, which has destroyed the majority of the organic components in the soil that would have contributed more to the soil organic matter.

Fig. 3. Interaction between Soil pH, OC, TEB and ECEC

Total exchangeable base (TEB) values for the soil horizons varied throughout the profiles, ranging from 4.58 to 9.17 cmol kg^{-1} . Exchangeable bases were ranked low to high in every profile that was looked at, and they were found on the exchange complex in the following order: $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^{+} > \text{Na}^{+}$. Abagyeh et al. (2019) results in the Guinea Savanna zone of Nigeria's soils were consistent with the profiles' total exchangeable basic cations. In the profiles, the soils' effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) ranged from 5.60 to 10.28 cmol kg^{-1} . Based on the ratings provided by Esu (1991), the profiles' ECEC was classified as medium. The quantity of ECEC of soil is determined by the kind amount of clay and organic matter. The Fig 3 shows the interaction between soil pH, OC, TEB and ECEC.

The Table 2 displays the micronutrient data from the profile pits located at the Mambilla Plateau. Throughout the profiles, the soils' accessible zinc levels varied from 0.010 to 0.022 mg kg^{-1} . the range of zero. According to Tisdale et al. (1995) and Esu (1991), the critical limit of zinc was determined to be 8 mg kg^{-1} or less than 1.00 mg kg^{-1} . It was discovered that the soils in the profiles' horizons deficient in zinc. Values for the Zn content fluctuated between 0.012 and 0.020 mg kg^{-1} throughout the profiles' surface horizons. Chesworth (1991) did note minimal mobility of zinc, though, as seen by the near values of the metal in the subsurface and surface soils. In all of the profiles, the available zinc did not exhibit a particular distribution trend with profile depth. Furthermore, the fact that Zn in some profiles declines with depth implies that plants might not have a Zn "store" on the lower

surface. This is related to research done in the Guinea Savanna region of Nigeria's soils by Mustapha et al. (2011). The differences in Zn availability across and within the profiles' horizons are consistent with Jobbágy and Jackson's (2001) findings that micronutrients may be transported from one soil horizon to another by leaching.

Table 2. *Micronutrients of the soils of Mambilla Plateau*

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Zn	Mn	Cu	Fe
		→ mg/kg ←			
Profile 1(Jabu) (N06°53'52.8" E011°24'13.9" and elevation= 1567 m)					
Ap	0 – 29	0.017	0.026	4.2	0.37
Bt1	29 -48	0.016	0.025	3.6	0.32
Bt2	48 – 71	0.015	0.024	3.2	0.27
Bt3	71 – 86	0.014	0.022	3.1	0.25
Bt4	86 – 120	0.015	0.023	3.4	0.28
Bt5	120 – 180	0.015	0.023	3.8	0.26
Profile 2 (Tonga Shaibu) (N06° 51'11.5" E011°23'06.05" and elevation= 1435 m)					
Ap	0 – 54	0.013	0.026	3.6	0.27
Bt1	54 – 85	0.012	0.027	3.7	0.28
Bt2	85 – 126	0.014	0.028	3.8	0.29
Bt3	126 – 144	0.015	0.024	3.4	0.25
Bt4	144 – 160	0.013	0.023	3.3	0.24
Profile 3 (Dembe) (N06°45'05.30" E011°20'02.7" and elevation= 1275 m)					
Ap	0 – 30	0.016	0.025	4.3	0.38
A	30 – 39	0.018	0.027	3.8	0.29
AB1	39 – 49	0.017	0.026	3.6	0.28
AB2	49 – 60	0.014	0.023	3.5	0.25
Bt	60 – 70	0.013	0.021	3.3	0.23
C1	70 – 83	0.011	0.020	3.1	0.21
C2	83 -106	0.012	0.023	3.2	0.20
Profile 4 (Kune) (N06°43'24.4" E011°21'56.7" and elevation= 1271 m)					
Ap	0 – 32	0.017	0.026	4.2	0.38
A1	32 – 65	0.019	0.028	5.3	0.41
A2	65 – 90	0.018	0.027	5.2	0.40
A3	90 – 113	0.020	0.032	5.1	0.43
A4	113 – 138	0.016	0.025	4.8	0.38
Bt1	138- 165	0.018	0.027	4.6	0.39
Bt2	165 – 200	0.017	0.026	3.8	0.28
Profile 5 (Mbanga) (N06°37'03.4" E011°12'28.1" and elevation= 1481 m)					
Ap	0 – 40	0.017	0.028	3.9	0.29
A	40 – 89	0.014	0.025	3.6	0.25
Bt1	89 – 122	0.012	0.021	3.4	0.24
Bt2	122 – 160	0.013	0.020	3.3	0.22
C	160 – 200	0.015	0.024	4.4	0.25
Profile 6 (Dung) (N06°40'34.1" E011°18'27.4" and elevation= 1272 m)					
Ap	0 – 25	0.012	0.026	3.2	0.27
Bt1	25 – 49	0.013	0.024	3.3	0.25
Bt2	49 – 130	0.014	0.022	3.3	0.23
Bt3	130 – 200	0.013	0.020	3.0	0.21

Table 2. Micronutrients of the soil of Mambilla Plateau (cont'd)

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Zn	Mn	Cu	Fe
		mg/kg			
Profile 7 (Leme) (N06°45'15.1" E011°12'34.6" and elevation= 1539 m)					
A	0 – 11	0.020	0.023	5.1	0.45
Bt1	11 – 42	0.018	0.025	4.3	0.38
Bt2	42 – 71	0.017	0.024	4.4	0.35
Bt3	71 – 87	0.019	0.027	4.2	0.36
Bt4	87 – 120	0.017	0.025	3.9	0.33
C1	120 – 164	0.019	0.026	4.8	0.37
C2	164 – 200	0.022	0.028	3.7	0.29
Profile 8 (Yerimaru) (3N06°47'39.4" E011°02'42.1" and elevation= 1522 m)					
Ap	0 – 25	0.019	0.030	3.9	0.35
Bt1	25 – 45	0.014	0.027	2.8	0.27
Bt2	45 – 115	0.013	0.028	3.2	0.25
Bt3	115 – 132	0.013	0.026	3.3	0.26
Bt4	132 – 200	0.017	0.024	3.1	0.21
Profile 9 (Furumi) (N06°53'51.8" E011°04'00.7" and elevation= 1497 m)					
Ap	0 – 21	0.012	0.028	3.8	0.31
Bt1	21 – 35	0.013	0.029	3.6	0.34
Bt2	35 – 100	0.010	0.027	3.4	0.27
Bt3	100 – 140	0.010	0.024	3.3	0.22
Bt4	140 – 186	0.012	0.021	3.5	0.26
Bt5	186 – 200	0.013	0.023	3.3	0.21
Profile 10 (Nguroje) (N06°53'00.8" E011°07'54.8" and elevation= 1499 m)					
Ap	0 – 30	0.014	0.023	3.8	0.35
Bt1	30 – 62	0.016	0.025	3.7	0.34
Bt2	62 – 93	0.018	0.027	3.6	0.31
Bt3	93 – 122	0.019	0.028	3.4	0.29
Bt4	122 – 140	0.017	0.026	3.2	0.28
Bt5	140 – 180	0.014	0.023	3.0	0.26
Profile 11(NgelNyake) (N07°05'27.6" E011°05'17.0" and elevation= 1608 m)					
Ap	0 – 34	0.018	0.031	4.5	0.38
A	34 – 87	0.019	0.034	5.3	0.39
BA	87 – 114	0.017	0.028	4.8	0.33
Bt1	114 – 132	0.013	0.027	4.6	0.27
Bt2	132 – 158	0.012	0.024	3.9	0.26
Bt3	158 – 200	0.013	0.020	3.4	0.24
Profile 12 (Maisamari) (N07°10'16.1" E011°05'09.0" and elevation= 1440 m)					
Ap	0 – 20	0.018	0.026	3.9	0.38
A1	20 – 43	0.017	0.026	4.0	0.38
A2	43 – 84	0.016	0.024	3.8	0.28
A3	84 – 111	0.022	0.029	4.2	0.43
A4	111 – 174	0.021	0.028	4.1	0.41
AB	174 – 200	0.019	0.026	3.8	0.39

The profiles of the Mambilla Plateau showed accessible manganese (Mn) contents ranging from 0.020 to 0.034 mg kg⁻¹. Mn levels in the surface horizons varied throughout the profiles, ranging from 0.023 to 0.031 mg kg⁻¹. According to Tisdale et al. (1995), the manganese concentrations in the soils in the profile horizons were below the critical threshold of 1–4 mg kg⁻¹. The measured Mn concentrations were below the range of 11.2 – 20.50 mg kg⁻¹ discovered in the soils of the Northern Nigerian Savanna by Oyinlola and Chude (2010). In a similar vein, Rengel (2007) found that organic residue influences manganese's immediate and potential availability in soil.

The profiles' accessible copper (Cu) contents ranged from 2.8 to 5.3 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 2). The range of 0.2 to 1.0 mg kg⁻¹ given by Esu (1991) as the critical level was exceeded by the available Cu in the soils of the profiles as described, although Tisdale *et al.* (1995) suggested a critical value of 2.5 to 4.5 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu. Cu levels in the surface horizons of the profiles ranged from 3.2 to 5.1 mg kg⁻¹. The previous findings of Hassan and Ogbonaya (2016) and Mulima *et al.* (2015) on the extremely low content of Cu for some sandy soils of the savannah biological zone are contradicted by the substantial Cu values found in all of the profile pits. Cu availability is not a characteristic of fertile soil. Despite the high Cu levels, they were within the predicted limits (< 100 mg kg⁻¹) for tropical soils and consistent with the results reported by Salisu *et al.* (2016). Both the parent materials and the use of agrochemicals may have an impact on the high content (Mustapha *et al.*, 2017; Salisu *et al.*, 2016). Cu may interfere antagonistically with macro- and micronutrients, causing harm to plant roots, thus it's important to be aware of any potential hazardous effects on plants (Silva *et al.*, 2019). In different profiles, the distribution of copper along the depth of the profile followed an uneven pattern. According to Jiang *et al.* (2006), the variance can be linked to anthropogenic disturbance, leaching, and the accumulation of nutrients in the topsoil. Exchangeable bases may leach to lower depths, which could explain the rising Cu content with depth. Similar findings were achieved by Domchang *et al.* (2014) and Saddiq *et al.* (2008), who connected higher clay and exchangeable bases with Cu availability.

Fig. 4. Interaction between the selected soil micronutrients

Across the profiles, the soils' accessible iron (Fe) content ranged from 0.21 to 0.45 mg kg⁻¹. The profiles' soils had less iron in them than the recommended thresholds of >2.5 mg kg⁻¹ (Tisdale *et al.*, 1995) and >4.5 mg kg⁻¹ (Esu, 1991). On the other hand, the profiles' surface horizons showed Fe concentrations ranging from 0.27 to 0.45 mg kg⁻¹. This result contradicts the findings on the soils of the Guinea savanna zone of Nigeria reported by

Mustapha et al. (2010) and Oyinlola and Chude (2010). Taking these essential limits into account, it was discovered that every profile pit was within the inadequate range. In every profile, the distribution of Fe content showed an uneven pattern down the profile depth. Thus, despite the fact that the soils under study were acidic, the low concentration of accessible iron raises the possibility that the soil's total iron content may be low. The Fig 4 shows the interaction between the studied micronutrients.

According to Rattan et al. (2008), the degree of variation in the soils' overall micronutrient content reflects the variety of parent materials from which they have come. The total micronutrient content of the soil is determined by parent material and pedogenic processes. The depletion of accessible micronutrients in soils is exacerbated by leaching loss of micronutrients, liming of soils, limited use of manures, and usage of excessive micronutrient fertilizers devoid of micronutrient additions (Saye et al., 2021). Higher micronutrient concentration was found on the soil surface, according to Ivana et al. (2015), who also linked the higher micronutrient content to increased crop residue decomposition and soil organic matter breakdown. Due to various soil and climatic factors, such as high rainfall, light texture, abundance of Fe and Al oxides, slow rate of organic matter decomposition, and high critical levels of nutrient availability, the deficiencies are even more severe in acidic soils (Saye et al., 2021; Singh, 2007). In most tropical soils, micronutrient deficiencies and soil acidity are the main factors limiting the productivity of a wide variety of crops (Singh, 2007; Kumar, 2001).

Table 3. *The relationship between micronutrient and selected soil properties*

Soil properties	Zn	Mn	Cu	Fe
	mg/kg			
Sand (g/kg)	0.473**	0.297*	0.431**	0.447**
Silt (g/kg)	-0.173	-0.251*	-0.162	-0.166
Clay (g/kg)	-0.479**	0.200*	-0.434**	-0.452**
pH(H ₂ O)	-0.001	-0.027	-0.214	-0.074
OC (g/kg)	0.434**	0.367**	0.403**	0.549**
TEB (cmol/kg)	0.445**	0.273*	0.188	0.344**
ECEC (cmol/kg)	0.424**	0.266*	0.153	0.323**

OC= organic carbon, TEB= total exchangeable bases, ECEC= effective cation exchange capacity, *= significant at correlation level ($p < 0.05$), **= significant at correlation level ($p < 0.01$)

The result as indicated in Table 3 showed that available Zn correlated positively and highly significant ($r = 0.473$, $r = 0.434$, $r = 0.445$, $r = 0.424$, $p = 0.01$) with sand, OC, TEB and ECEC while, it had a highly significant negative relationship ($r = -0.479$, $p = 0.01$) with clay. Available Mn had a positive significant relationship ($r = 0.297$, $r = 0.200$, $r = 0.273$, $r = 0.266$, $p = 0.05$) with sand, clay, TEB and ECEC while it had a highly significant relationship ($r = 0.367$, $p = 0.01$) with OC. Available Cu had a positive correlation ($r = 0.188$, $r = 0.153$) with TEB and ECEC while, it had a highly significant positive relationship ($r = 0.431$, $r = 0.403$, $p = 0.01$) with sand and OC. Available Fe had a high significant positive relationship ($r = 0.447$, $r = 0.549$, $r = 0.344$, $r = 0.323$, $p = 0.01$) with sand, OC, TEB and ECEC. Silt correlated negatively ($r = -0.173$, $r = -0.251$, $r = -0.162$, $r = -0.166$) with Zn, Mn, Cu and Fe. However, pH had a negative correlation with Zn, Mn, Cu and Fe. Similarly, Hassan et al. (2016) found that OC had a highly significant positive association with Cu and Mn, while Fe associated positively with silt and pH. However, pH linked adversely with Cu and Mn, although silt

correlated negatively with Fe and Mn, according to prior research by Oyinlola and Chude (2010). The relationship's direction is indicated by the coefficient's sign. The coefficient is positive if both variables tend to rise or decrease together, and negative if one variable tends to increase while the other decreases.

Conclusions

Deficits in micronutrients in the soil have an impact on how well plants grow and develop. Therefore, to guarantee food and nutritional security, nutrient stress needs to be efficiently addressed. Because each crop has a unique micronutrient requirement and because micronutrients have a functional relationship with one another, it is exceedingly challenging to generalize soil management techniques for preserving sufficient levels of micronutrients in soils. The toxicity and inadequacy levels of micronutrients in soil vary little, therefore location-specific knowledge and management are crucial. Therefore, the application of micronutrient fertilizer, the addition of soil amendments, and the adoption of better plant types could all help to minimize micronutrient deficiencies.

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